

**HR ANALYTICS AND ITS MODERATING FACTORS - A
REVIEW IN KASIM TEXTILE MILL PRIVATE LTD,
MADURAI**

B. Divya Bharathi*, Dr. K. Binith Muthukrishnan &
Dr. B. Velmurugan*****

* PG Scholar, Department of Management Studies, NPR College of Engineering & Technology,
Dindigul, Tamilnadu

** Associate Professor, Department of MBA, NPR College of Engineering & Technology, Dindigul, Tamilnadu

*** Associate professor & HOD, Department of Management Studies, NPR College of Engineering &
Technology, Dindigul, Tamilnadu

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Abstract:

This theoretical article elaborates the moderating factors of the human resources analysis (HR Analytics), considered as one of the main initiatives in human resources today. It seems that the analysis simplifies the decision-making process by proposing a more data-driven approach. Although human resource analysis is a priority in most organizations, the implementation process is slow and only a minor proportion of them even report having implemented it. HR analysis is not progressing as many academics have suggested over the last 10 years. Therefore, it seems necessary to identify the modulatory factors of HR Analytics that promote or hinder its success. The number of academic research articles dealing with this subject is very small. The impact of moderating factors on the level of human resource analysis is vague and unexplored. This paper offers potential explanations of the relationship between moderators and HR analysis and provides suggestions to organizations on how best to address these factors. In the first part of this article, the development and theoretical assumptions for a more data-driven approach to human resource decision making are developed. Then the concept of HR Analytics will be defined. The third section presents case studies and examines the importance of the practice of human resource analysis in organizations. In the following, each moderation factor will be examined in detail. Finally, the main conclusions of the subject under study are discussed and summarized.

Key Words: HR Analytics, People Analytics, HR Metrics, Big Data, Strategic HRM.

Introduction:

The purpose of this article is to address the question why HR Analytics is not progressing, as it is proposed by many academics. In doing so, this article provides a review of high quality research, related to the moderation of factors that promote or prevent HR Analytics' success. However, high quality research on HR Analytics's value is quite rare. On the one hand, most articles are published by consultants with business interest and more based on beliefs than proofs. On the other hand, most of the reported HR Analytics successful stories have a narrow focus and deal with topics as a daytime. The purpose of this article is not only to identify and describe moderate factors of HR Analytics. I am still trying to provide a better understanding of how moderation factors influence the level of H. Analysis and show how organizations best deal with these factors

Company Profile:

Kasim Textile Mills Private Limited, forayed into the textile business in 1991 by starting a small unit at Puliyankulam in Madurai, Tamil Nadu. Since its inception, the company has galvanized to prominence as one of the leading Manufacturer and Exporter of Greige/Grey Woven fabric under the able leadership of Mr. A. Shahul Hameed. He was steadfast in his mission to steer the fortunes of the organization with his sheer perseverance and humility. The company managed to sail thro challenging situations, thanks to the resolve of the management to never compromise on the quality of its product and its delivery schedule despite hostile business conditions. The company has achieved its Organic growth by delving itself into every least possible detail of quality adherence and living up to the expectation of the customer

Statement of the Problem:

The purpose of this study is to gain insight as to the reasons why more HR professionals are not using HRA to improve organizational performance in order to gain and maintain a competitive advantage. Could there be factors that may act as barriers that impede HR professionals' adoption of HRA. Practitioner research outlines the shortcomings of HR professionals when it comes to the use of analytics and metrics. The extant literature further reports that in many organizations, executives still view HR as a - cost centrel dealing primarily with soft skills. Executives may believe HR professionals analyse only what has happened, while lacking a perspective and a bottom-line mindset.

Objectives of the Study:

- To identify the role of analytics in human resource function.
- To find out the threat and opportunities of implementing and using human resource analytics

- This paper intends to explore and analyse Digital HR, digital transformation of HR services and processes through the use of social, mobile, analytics and cloud (SMAC) technologies.
- Digital HR represents a sea change in both the approach and execution, although it takes place on a continuum as organizations progress.

Need of the Study:

HR analytics is very important in human resources management. In HR functions, the use of analytical tools will help to grow at a faster rate and make evidence-based decisions. HR analytics collects and analyses past data with positive and negative trends. It readily compares organizational performance with competitors. HR analytics is important in workforce planning, competitive advantage, employee recruiting and retention, using data, producing findings and forecasts for organizations, performance appraisal, data manipulation, choosing suitable modelling methodologies, and other areas related t

Scope of the Study:

HR analytics, also referred to as people analytics, workforce analytics, or talent analytics, involves gathering together, analyzing, and reporting HR data. It enables your organization to measure the impact of a range of HR metrics on overall business performance and make decisions based on data. HR analytics doesn't collect data about how your employees are performing at work, instead, its sole aim is to provide better insight into each of the human resource processes, gathering related data and then using this data to make informed decisions on how to improve these processes

Hypothesis of the Study:

- Null Hypothesis HO: There is no significance relationship between Experience in years and Kinds of Human Resource Analytics describes strategy for HR analytics.
- Alternative Hypothesis H1: There is a significance relationship between Experience in years and Kinds of Human Resource Analytics describes strategy for HR analytics.

Research Design:

A research design is considered as the framework or plan for a study that guides as well as helps the data collection and analysis of data. The research design may be exploratory, descriptive and experimental for the present study. The descriptive research design is adopted for this project.

Research Methodology:

Research methodology is the systematic way to solve the research problem. It gives an idea about various steps adopted by the researcher in a systematic manner with an objective to determine various manners.

Sample Size:

The study sample constitutes 150 respondents constituting in the research area.

Sampling Design:

The researcher has used probability sampling in which stratified random sampling is used.

Collection of Data:

Most of the data collected by the researcher is primary data through personal interview, where the researcher and the respondent operate face - to - face.

Analysis of Data:

The data are collected through survey and books, reports, newspapers and internet etc., the survey conducted among the employees of home textiles. The data collected by the researcher are tabulated and analysed in such a way to make interpretations. Various steps, which are required to fulfil the purpose, i.e., editing, coding, and tabulating. Editing refers to separate, correct and modify the collected data. Coding refers to assigning number or other symbols to each answer for placing them in categories to prepare data for tabulation refers to bring together the similar data in rows and columns and totalling them in an accurate and meaningful manner The collected data are analysed and interrupted using statistical tools and techniques.

Methods of Data Collection:

- Primary Data: Primary goal is original and collected by the researcher freshly. In this study primary data was collected through questionnaire. A questionnaire is a popular means of collecting primary data. A questionnaire is a list of question for the own.
- Secondary Data: Secondary data is the data, which is already available. It can be obtained through company records, internet and some data collected from the observation method by the researcher.

Statistical Tools:

The statistical tools used for analysing the data collected are percentage method, chi square, bar diagrams and pie diagrams.

Tools for Analysis of Data:

- Simple Percentage Method
- Correlation
- Chi-square Method

Review of Literature:

Alper Ertürk (2017) the purpose of this study is to explore the way to enhance openness to organizational change of employees and their participation, managerial communication and trust in one's

supervisor. The results indicate that the relationship between managerial communication and openness to change mediates fully on one's supervisor, whereas it partially mediated the openness and employee participation relationship to change the employees.

Graham Mole (2017) organizational culture affects behavior in six aspects. First of all, organizational culture has as a guiding role. Organizational cultures not only clearly affect the highest or long-term objectives, but also target the organizational objectives as individuals' goals. The objectives set by the organization allow its members to feel the value of work and inspire the desire of succeeding.

Mohammad Essawi (2017) The author suggest constructive confrontation approach for organizational culture management which provides the details about the transformation of confrontation caused by values of newly declared organizational culture and employees current values in constructive process. The approach involves organizational cultural change planning and its adoption. The paper discusses about the merger and Acquisition of organizations. The author suggests that mergers and acquisitions make the organization risky especially when it is present in different countries, fails to achieve the intended benefits but adds values to shareholders.

Robert D (2018) the advantages organizational culture has on behavior is also reflected in leadership management. When making decisions, leaders have to confront many complex challenges. A leader's success depends on various factors, for instance on his knowledge and understanding of the organizational culture. The leader who understands his organization's culture and takes it seriously is capable of predicting the outcome of his decisions in preventing any anticipated consequences. It is notable that most human behavior is learned through imitation. In order to get employees to behave as expected, leaders' example is indispensable.

Suggestions:

- Human Resource Analytics is key element for changing HR leaders across all sectors. HR analytics shows trend for every employees going to leave the job or stay and track the performance of each employees.
- Recently, it is adopted by the textile industry for making better HR decisions. This research paper is conceptual in nature and based on secondary data sources such as research journals, magazines, newspapers, company reports on HR analytics.
- The analyses of given researches explores that Indian textile industry has just now awakened with the idea of adopting the big data analytics for better HR decisions. Indian textile sector is said to be at infancy stage unlike western business firms
- The prospects and ambition among business leaders to improve Human Resource practice and business outcome through analytics is growing rapidly in India. The analysis of papers illustrates that HR analytics in textile sector has been used more for recruitment, retention, reducing attrition rather than showing effect of HR analytics on entire business outcome.
- There are requirement of developing new HR metrics for business decision-making by the Indian textile companies. Lack of innovative technology, demand-supply gap exists, huge cost, rigidity of culture pose notable hurdles for the Indian textile sector to device big data analytics for the people. In addition to these challenges, important one is lack of analytical talent accessible for HR analytics.

Conclusion:

There is a vast scope for improving both individual and organizational performance through HR analytics. It becomes possible because through analytics one can identify the various areas where money, time and efforts can be better utilized. . Business analytics is being focused more than any other technology in the past decade. The popularization of big data and the subsequent development of analytical tools has greatly influenced the growth of business analytics. With more organizations adapting business analytics, organizations are obsessed to spread the application of analytics into all domains. Use of analytics in the field of HR has also gained momentum. Digitalization of HR dashboards has helped in producing updated insights about the organizations workforce status. HR analytics will also be helpful in assessing the strategic impact of HR on business and other core HR functions. Areas of talent planning, acquisition, retention, training, performance management and succession planning can be improved significantly by using the results of the organization's HR analytics. A review of various studies and the corresponding literature available about people analytics proves that there is a greater scope to position people analytics to use as a strategic enabler i.e., the one to play crucial role in defining the strategic decisions of the firm that have a bearing on the long-term performance of the company. The future of people analytics as an important function in organization is vast.

References:

1. Boudreau, J. W., & Ramstad, P. M. (2007). *Beyond HR: The new science of human capital*. Boston, MA: Harvard Business School Press.
2. Boudreau, J., & Lawler, E. E. (2014). Stubborn traditionalism in HRM: Causes and consequences. *Human Resource Management Review*, 24(3), 232–244. <http://doi.org/10.1016/j.hrmr.2014.03.005>
3. Douglas, B. G., & Young, M. B. (2015). Employee Trust Seen as Essential for HR Analytics, 14(8), 14–16.

4. Fecheyr-Lippens, Bruce; Schaninger, Bill; Tanner, K. (2015). Power to the new people analytics. McKinsey Quarterly, (1), 61–63. Retrieved from <http://www.mckinsey.com/business-functions/organization/our-insights/power-to-the-new-people-analytics#>
5. Gardner, N., Mcgranahan, D., & Wolf, W. (2011). Question for your HR chief: Are we using our “people data” to create value? McKinsey Quarterly, (2), 1–5.
6. Goldstein, J. (2015). Digital technology demand is transforming HR. Workforce Solutions Review, (November), 28–29.